

Methyl epijasmonate : Historical perspective and total synthesis

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Historical perspective, total synthesis and biological activities of methyl epijasmonate have been reviewed up to August, 1999.

Historical perspective

Since time immemorial, the odoriferous white blossoms of the jasmine plant, probably an Iranian native, have been used in India for ceremonial purposes and for the scenting of ointments¹. Nowadays jasmine flower oil and its synthetic substitutes are the key ingredients universally employed in the manufacture of high grade perfumes. If one looks at a GC trace of jasmine absolute, it becomes apparent that the product is a complex mixture. However, the major components of the mixture (benzyl acetate, benzyl benzoate, phytol etc.) are not the principal contributors to the characteristic odour of jasmine². Of the 200 or so compounds present in jasmine, the most important odoriferous components were initially believed to be jasmone (1) and methyl jasmonate (2).

Methyl jasmonate (2) was first isolated and characterized in 1962 from the essential oil of *Jasminum grandiflorum* L. by Demole *et al.*³. Subsequently in 1967, the same compound was also isolated from *Rosmarinus officinalis* L. by Crabalona⁴. With the passage of time, the jasmonoid family continued to grow and by 1977 two more

cluding an industrial synthesis^{7a}; even afterwards, the synthetic activities continued unabated^{7b-g} thereby adding one more industrial synthesis^{7c}. The synthetic material obviously gave a new dimension to the perfume industry owing to its relatively low price. The occurrence of the C-2 epimer of

methyl jasmonate (2), namely, methyl epijasmonate (6), a pheromone synergist, was first reported by Baker *et al.*⁸ in 1981, who isolated both the epimers from the hairpencils of the male oriental fruit moth, *Grapholitha molesta* B.

In 1984, Vick and Zimmerman reported the biosynthesis of jasmonic acid as portrayed in Scheme 1⁹. The key steps here include the formation of 12-oxophytodienoic acid (12-oxo-PDA) (9) from linolenic acid (8) by the action of a lipoxygenase/cyclase, which then produces a cascade of

new members with potent plant growth inhibitory activities, namely, jasmonic acid (3)⁵ and cucurbitic acid (4)⁶, the latter isolated from seeds of *Cucurbita pepo* L. (pumpkin) were added to this group. The period 1962-1981 witnessed frenetic activities among organic chemists for the synthesis of methyl jasmonate in view of its importance in the perfume industry, and by 1981, seventeen different total syntheses of 2 were recorded in the chemical literature^{7a,b} in-

Scheme 1

† Dedicated to Professor D. Nasipuri on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.

products, e.g. 3-oxo-2-*cis*-(pent-2*Z*-enyl)cyclopentyl-octanoic acid (OPC-8:0) (**10**), OPC-6:0 (**11**), OPC-4:0 (**12**) and *cis*-(*Z*)- or epijasmonic acid (**7**) via a number of β -oxidation steps. The mechanism outlined in Scheme 1 demands that the biosynthetic product has the *cis*-arrangement of the side chains about the cyclopentane ring, implying that epijasmonic acid (**7**) is the initial product of the oxidative cascade. This led Vick and Zimmerman to make the provocative statement at this juncture in that ".....the *trans*-form of methyl jasmonate (**2**) or jasmonic acid (**3**) reported by others may have been the result of epimerization of the *cis*-compound at C-2 during the purification procedure. Each of these procedures employed either acidic extraction conditions or high temperature fractional distillation....". Interestingly, at about the same time, Nishida and Acree¹⁰ reported the occurrence of methyl epijasmonate (**6**) in lemon peel, free from its C-2 epimer, e.g. **2**. These observations raised the question as to the relative configuration of the biologically active substances. A year later (1985), Acree and Nishida¹¹ obtained the pure stereoisomers **2**, **6** and their enantiomers **13**, **14** by tedious separation procedures and confirmed that only (+)-*Z*-methyl epijasmonate (**6**) which readily isomerizes to (-)-*Z*-methyl jasmonate (**2**) is fragrant. This was further corroborated by Weinges *et al.*¹² who synthesized (-)-*Z*-methyl jasmonate (**2**) from catalpol as starting material and found that the synthetic material is totally odourless. These new findings soon heralded a new era in

jasmonoid research. Chemists in far-flung laboratories are now busy digging into newer sources of jasmonoids and/or discovering newer members of this family as well as their hitherto undiscovered biological activities¹³. More recently, (-)-jasmonic acid (**3**) and (+)-epijasmonic acid (**7**) have been reported as constituents of the Black Sea red alga, *Gelidium latifolium*¹⁴. In addition, methyl cucurbate (**5**) has also been isolated from *Boronia megastigma*¹⁵.

Jasmonates have triggered intense research activities from the point of view of structure-odour relationship studies¹⁶. In addition, they are now receiving renewed interest as po-

tentially important signalling molecules for communication between plants¹⁷ as well as mediators of phytoalexin production in response to fungal attack¹⁸. This is because these compounds markedly increase the expression of specific plant genes, some of which are wound responsive. Jasmonates also display several other biological activities such as inhibition of growth^{18c,19}, promotion of coiling in tendrils of climbing plants²⁰ and the induction of tubers in potato stolons¹⁹. It may be mentioned here that isolated natural jasmonic acid equilibrates to the more stable *trans*-arrangement (actual equilibrium for **3** and **7** equals 95 : 5)¹⁰. Although it was suspected that the *cis*-isomer was the physiologically active one²¹, recent researchers failed to indicate whether the observed biological activities reside in either the *cis*, *trans*, or both isomers²².

Syntheses

In comparison with most present-day synthetic targets, methyl epijasmonate possesses a deceptively simple-looking structure. Its synthesis, however, has strict stereochemical requirements in view of the epimerizable *cis* attachments to the cyclopentane ring. Moreover, the double bond configuration of the C-2 side-chain must be *Z*. A continuous endeavor spanning a period of more than 15 years has now resulted in 18 original contributions in the field. All the syntheses developed up to now for methyl epijasmonate (**6**) can be divided into three sub-sections, namely, (a) non-enantioselective (racemic) syntheses, (b) enantioselective (asymmetric) syntheses and (c) enantiospecific (chiral pool) syntheses.

Non-enantioselective (racemic) syntheses :

The first synthesis of (\pm)-methyl epijasmonate (**6**) was reported by Tanaka and Torii in 1975 as portrayed in Scheme 2²³. It may be noted that their actual target was methyl jasmonate (**2**) and not its C-2 epimer **6**, since the latter was isolated and characterized much later (*vide supra*). The synthesis starts from 2-cyclopentenone (**15**) which was transformed to aldehyde **17** via a sequence involving cycloaddition reaction, *cis*-diol formation of **16** with KMnO_4 , NaBH_4 reduction and treatment with NaIO_4 . Partial oxidation of aldehyde **17**, then esterification of resulting acid hemiacetal followed by treatment with a catalytic amount of *p*-toluenesulfonic acid in methanol gave a mixture of acetal ester **18** (65%) and lactone ester **19** (10%). The mixture was chromatographed over silica gel to give pure **18**. The thioacetalization of ester **18** gave **20** which, on hydrolysis followed by a 'salt-free' Wittig reaction, afforded the bridged lactone **21**. Subsequent basic hydrolysis and esterification with CH_2N_2 yielded (\pm)-**5** which, on Jones oxidation, gave

(±)-6. Concerning the purity of this synthetic product, several other workers^{24,25} raised questions, since the oxidative step 5 → 6 must have caused significant epimerization at C-2 in view of the prolonged reaction time. In addition, the

Scheme 2. Reagents and condition : (a) 1,4-butadiene, 110°, (b) KMnO_4 - MgSO_4 , MeOH, (c) NaBH_4 , EtOH, (d) NaIO_4 , (e) KMnO_4 - MgSO_4 , Me_2CO (aq.), (f) $\text{CH}_2\text{N}_2/\text{Et}_2\text{O}$, (g) PTSA, MeOH, reflux, (h) $\text{BF}_3\cdot\text{Et}_2$, $\text{HS}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{SH}$, moist CHCl_3 , (i) $\text{HgCl}_2\text{-HgO}$, CH_3CN aq., (j) salt-free $\text{Ph}_3\text{P}=\text{CHEt}$, (k) KOH aq., MeOH, (l) $\text{CH}_2\text{N}_2/\text{Et}_2\text{O}$, (m) $\text{Na}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7/\text{H}^+$, CH_2Cl_2 .

synthetic product is also contaminated with *ca.* 5% of the (*E*)-isomer.

In 1987, Kitahara and co-workers reported the synthesis of (±)-6 as described in Scheme 3²⁶. Chlorination of diketone 23 followed by treatment with Na_2CO_3 gave 2-substituted cyclopentenone 24 which was transformed to allyl acetate 25 via a three-step sequence involving ozonolysis, reduction with LiAlH_4 and acetylation. Nucleophilic displacement of acetate 25 with sodiomalonate followed by decarboxylation gave 26. The hydroboration-oxidation of 26 gave a mixture of 27 and its *trans*-isomer 28 in a ratio of 1 : 2. Deacetalization of 27 followed by a 'salt-free' Wittig reaction gave a mixture of (±)-methyl cucurbitate (5) and the bridged lactone 21. Finally, oxidation of 5 under Brown's conditions gave (±)-6 and (±)-2 in a ratio of 88 : 12. Synthetic (±)-6 was obtained from 23 in 10 steps, in an overall yield of 1%.

Scheme 3. Reagents and condition : (a) *t*-BuOCl, CHCl_3 , (b) Na_2CO_3 , xylene, (c) O_3 , MeOH, PTSA, (d) LiAlH_4 , then Ac_2O , Py, (e) $\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_4$, $\text{NaCH}(\text{CO}_2\text{Me})_2$, (f) NaCl , DMSO, (g) $\text{BH}_3\cdot\text{Me}_2\text{S}$, H_2O_2 , OH^- , (h) H^+ , (i) salt-free $\text{Ph}_3\text{P}=\text{CHEt}$, (j) $\text{H}_2\text{CrO}_4/\text{Et}_2\text{O}$.

A stereoselective synthesis of (±)-methyl epijasmonate (6) was reported by Crombie and Mistry²⁷ in 1988 (Scheme 4). In this synthesis, diene 30²⁸ was prepared by [3,3]-sigmatropic rearrangement of 5-vinyl-2-norbornene (29) which is commercially available as a mixture of *endo* and *exo* isomers (ratio 67 : 33). Only the *endo* isomer participates in thermal rearrangement. Differential oxidation at the cyclohexane double bond in 30 using hypobromous acid,

Scheme 4. Reagents and condition : (a) 250°, (b) HOBr, THF, (c) KOBu^t , (d) CrO_3 , (e) KI_3 , Na_2CO_3 aq., (f) Bu_3SnH , AIBN, (g) DIBAL, THF, -30°, (h) NaH , $\text{Ph}_3\text{P}(\text{Pr})\text{Br}$, DMSO, 70°, (i) $\text{CH}_2\text{N}_2/\text{Et}_2\text{O}$, (j) PDC.

and conversion of the resulting bromohydrin to the epoxide with *t*-BuOK, followed by oxidation gave *cis*-dicarboxylic acid **31**. Iodolactonization of diacid **31** followed by deiodination using Bu₃SnH and AIBN gave lactone **32** which was transformed to hydroxy ester **22** via a three-step sequence involving reduction with DIBAL, Wittig reaction under 'salt-free' conditions and esterification with CH₂N₂. GC analysis of the silyl ether of **22** showed an 85 : 15 (*Z*) / (*E*) ratio. Pure (*Z*)-isomer was obtained by chromatography on AgNO₃-impregnated (15%) silica gel. Finally oxidation of **22** with PDC in dichloromethane gave (±)-**6**. HPLC analysis showed the presence of a small amount of its epimer **2**. The overall yield of (±)-**6** from **29** was 4% in 10 steps.

Scheme 5. Reagents and condition : (a) CCl₃CHO, AlCl₃, CH₂Cl₂, (b) Zn, AcOH, Et₂O, (c) PCC, 3 Å mol. sieves, (d) 95% H₂SO₄, 79% yield in three steps, (e) H₂O₂, H⁺, MeOH, (f) DIBAL, -78°, (g) salt-free Ph₃P=CHEt, (h) KOH aq., MeOH, (i) CH₂N₂/Et₂O, (j) PCC, 4 Å mol. sieves, 84% yield in three steps.

In another variation of the same theme, Seto and Yoshioka (1990) transformed norbornene **33** into (±)-**6** in a stereocontrolled fashion as shown in Scheme 5²⁵. The key intermediate **19** in this case was prepared via a highly regio- and chemoselective Baeyer-Villiger oxidation of **36** based on remote substituent control. The latter was prepared from norbornene **33** in four steps involving reaction with chloral in the presence of AlCl₃ as catalyst to give tricyclic compound **34**, reductive cleavage of the β, β, β-trichloroethyl ether moiety in **34** with Zn powder and acetic acid, oxidation of the resulting hydroxynorbornene **35** and acidic hydrolysis. DIBAL reduction of **19** followed by a 'salt-free' Wittig reaction yielded lactone **21**. The remaining steps are the same as in Torii's synthesis (*cf.* Scheme 2)²³. The overall yield of (±)-**6** from **33** was 41%. Though this synthesis is fully stereocontrolled, surprisingly these authors did not mention anything about the olefinic (*E/Z*) purity of their synthetic product **21** obtained at the Wittig step. It may be noted, however, that other workers^{29,30} have observed the formation of at least 4–11% of (*E*)-isomer in the same step.

Kitahara's second synthesis of (±)-methyl epijasmonate (**6**) reported in 1991, followed an entirely different strategy so as to afford the targeted natural product in a stereocontrolled manner as shown in Scheme 6³¹. In this synthesis, *cis*-oxaindan-1-one derivative **39** was used as the key intermediate. This was obtained from 3-oxocyclopentane carboxylic acid **37** (prepared from diethyl itaconate in three

Scheme 6. Reagents and condition : (a) CH(OMe)₃, TsOH, (b) LiAlH₄, then HCl, (c) BrCH₂CH(OMe)₂, TsOH, (d) *t*-BuOK, (e) LiAlH₄, (f) MEMCl, *i*-Pr₂NEt, (g) 80% AcOH aq., (h) salt-free Ph₃P=CHEt, (i) TsCl, (j) NaCN, (k) H₃O⁺, (l) alc. NaOH (m) CH₂N₂, (n) H₂CrO₄.

steps³²) by a four-step sequence involving protection of ketone, reduction to alcohol **38**, *trans*-acetalization followed by intramolecular alkylation. In order to prevent epimerization of the side-chain after cleavage of the cyclic acetal ring, the carbonyl group of **39** was reduced and protected as a MEM ether to give **40**. Selective hydrolysis of the cyclic acetal **40** followed by a 'salt-free' Wittig reaction gave (*Z*)-olefin **41** as the sole product. One-carbon homologation via a cyanide and deprotection gave methyl ester **22**. Finally oxidation under mild conditions gave (±)-**6** with 97% GC purity.

Stork and Ouerfelli³³ reported the synthesis of (±)-methyl epijasmonate (**6**) in 1992 as shown in Scheme 7. Here epoxidation of 2-cyclopentenone (**42**) followed by Horner-Wittig olefination gave **43**, which on reduction with activated zinc and copper(II) acetate in a mixture of water, methanol and saturated aqueous ammonium chloride (1 : 1 : 1) afforded hydroxy ester **44**. It may be noted that this reduction system proved to be the most efficient of a variety of other methods that were tried, including lithium in liquid ammonia, samarium iodide, iron powder, etc. Treatment of **44** with ethyl vinyl ether and *N*-iodosuccinimide yielded iodoacetal **45**, which on stereocontrolled radical cyclization

gave bicyclic acetal **46**. Acidic hydrolysis of **46** followed by a 'salt-free' Wittig reaction gave a mixture of hydroxy ester **22** and the related lactone **21** in the ratio 1 : 2. Lactone **21** was converted to the epijasmonate precursor **22** by methanolysis. Finally, Jones oxidation of **22** gave (\pm)-**6**, contaminated with *ca.* 5–10% of the (*E*)-isomer.

Scheme 7. Reagents and condition : (a) H_2O_2 , K_2HPO_4 , (b) $(\text{MeO})_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{CH}(\text{Na})\text{CO}_2\text{Me}$, (c) Zn , $\text{Cu}(\text{OAc})_2$, MeOH : H_2O : NH_4Cl satd. (1 : 1 : 1), (d) NIS , $\text{CH}_2=\text{CHOEt}$, (e) Bu_3SnH , AIBN , (f) H_3O^+ , (g) salt-free $\text{Ph}_3\text{P}=\text{CHEt}$, (h) NaOMe , (i) Jones' oxidation.

Scheme 8. Reagents and condition : (a) DHP , H , (b) $(\text{COCl})_2$, DMSO , (c) $\text{LiC}\equiv\text{C}(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{TMS}$, THF-HMPA , -78° , (d) $i\text{-BuMgBr}$, Cp_2TiCl_2 (cat.), (e) TBDPSCl , Im , (f) PPTS , EtOH , (g) $(\text{COCl})_2$, DMSO , (h) $(\text{MeO})_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{CH}(\text{Li})\text{CO}_2\text{Me}$, (i) 235° , 18 h, (j) 57% HI aq., benzene, (k) O_3 , (l) $\text{Ph}_3(\text{Pr})\text{PBr}$, $\text{NaN}(\text{TMS})_2$, THF , (m) $n\text{-Bu}_4\text{NF}$, THF , (n) $\text{H}_2\text{CrO}_4/\text{ether}$.

In 1994, Sarkar *et al.*³⁴ reported the synthesis of (\pm)-methyl epijasmonate (**6**) as portrayed in Scheme 8. Central to this approach is the synthesis of functionalized 1,6-diene **50** containing a homoallylsilane unit as ene donor which was transformed into the allylsilane **51** through a highly diastereoselective 5-(3,4)ene cyclization³⁵. In this reaction, three contiguous chiral centres were created with 100% *cis*-diastereoselectivity and 88% *trans*-diastereofacial selectivity by the influence of an oxygen substituent as a stereodirecting resident group in the ene component. Compound **50** was obtained from alcohol **49** via a sequence involving *t*-butyldiphenylsilyl ether protection, deprotection of the THP ether, Swern oxidation and Horner-Wittig reaction. Alcohol **49** was obtained from commercially available 1,4-butanediol (**47**) by a four-step sequence involving monoprotection, oxidation, formation of propargylic alcohol from the resulting aldehyde **48** and stereoselective reduction of the triple bond. Protodesilylation of **51** with a two-phase HI -benzene, water mixture followed by ozonolysis gave epijasmonoid building block **52**. Wittig olefination under 'salt-free' conditions followed by exposure to $n\text{-Bu}_4\text{NF}$ gave pure (\pm)-**5**. The minor C1- β isomer (11%) carried over from **51** was eliminated at this stage presumably via lactone formation to **21**. It may be mentioned here that this is the first synthesis of (\pm)-**5** wherein three chiral centres on the cyclopentane ring were created in proper stereochemical relationship in a single operation. The previous syntheses were either non-stereoselective or required an inversion of hydroxyl stereochemistry. Finally, oxidation of (\pm)-**5** with chromic acid under Brown's condition yielded (\pm)-**6** (90% *cis* selectivity).

Very recently, Clive *et al.*³⁶ have reported a formal synthesis of (\pm)-methyl epijasmonate (**6**) as described in Scheme 9. The key step here involves radical 5-*endo*-trigonal cyclization of **55** with Ph_3SnH and AIBN to give compound **56**, contaminated with chromatographically inseparable impurities. LiAlH_4 reduction of **56**, cleavage of both C-Si and O-Si bonds by treatment with $n\text{-Bu}_4\text{NF}$ in warm DMF followed by primary alcohol protection gave alcohol **57**. The impurities carried over from **56** were removed in the last step. Inversion of the stereochemistry at C-1 of alcohol **57** was effected by a four-step sequence involving protection of secondary alcohol, deprotection of the silyl ether, dehydration and rehydration. Replacement of the primary hydroxyl group of **58** by cyanide, hydrogenolysis to remove the benzyl protection, then PCC oxidation and a 'salt-free' Wittig reaction yielded the (*Z*)-olefin **59**. This completes a formal synthesis of (\pm)-methyl epijasmonate (**6**) since **59** has been previously transformed into the target molecule as

described in Scheme 6³¹.

Enantioselective (asymmetric) syntheses :

In 1989, the first enantioselective synthesis of (-)-methyl epijasmonate (**6**), the unnatural antipode, as well as a formal synthesis of (+)-methyl epijasmonate (**6**) were re-

Scheme 9. Reagents and condition : (a) $C_6H_{11}N(Pr-i)Li$, $PhSeCH_2CO_2Me$, -78° , (b) $TFA-H_2O$ (1 : 1), (c) $HC\equiv CCH_2OBn$, $BuLi$, (d) $(t-Bu)_2SiHCl$, Im , (e) Ph_3SnH , $AIBN$, (f) $LiAlH_4$, (g) $TBAF$, DMF , (h) $TBDPSCI$, Im , 33% in four steps, (i) $MEMCl$, $i-Pr_2NEt$, (j) $TBAF$, THF , (k) $o-O_2NC_6H_4SeCN$, Bu_3P , THF , $MCPBA$, $i-Pr_2NEt$, CH_2Cl_2 , (l) $BH_3 \cdot Me_2S$, $H_2O_2-OH^-$, (m) $TsCl$, (n) $NaCN$, (o) H_2 , 5% $Pd-C$, (p) PCC , 4 Å mol. sieves, (q) $(TMS)_2NK$, $Ph_3P(Pr)Br$.

ported by Montforts *et al.*³⁰ as described in Scheme 10³⁰. Palladium(0)-catalyzed enantiodivergent alkylation of cyclopent-2-ene-1,3-diol derivative **60** with sodiomalonate gave diester **61**. Demethoxycarbonylation of **61** followed by amide-acetal-Claisen rearrangement yielded *cis*-disubstituted cyclopentene **62**. Iodolactonization of **62** followed by radical cyclization gave lactone ester **63** which, on treatment with DIBAL followed by Wittig reaction under 'salt-free' conditions, gave bridged lactone **64** (*Z/E* = 96 : 4). Saponification of **64** followed by esterification gave alcohol **65**. Finally, Jones oxidation of **65** gave a mixture of (-)-**6** and (+)-**6** (60 : 40). Purification of the mixture by HPLC gave pure (-)-**6**. In addition, Montforts *et al.* also synthesized *ent*-**61** from *ent*-**60** which in principle could be converted into (+)-**6**.

In 1990, Helmchen *et al.*³⁷ disclosed the first enantioselective synthesis of (+)-methyl epijasmonate (**6**) as highlighted in Scheme 11. Here in the first stage, ester **68**, was converted into iodolactone **69** via a three-step sequence

involving Diels-Alder reaction with cyclopentadiene, basic hydrolysis and lactonization by using KI_3 . In the second stage decarboxylative 1,3-elimination of the dried K- salt of **69** gave **70**. In the third stage, basic hydrolysis of **70** followed by oxidation with $RuO_4(cat)/NaIO_4$ gave keto carboxylic acid **71** which was converted to lactone acid **72**, via HI addition, reduction and epoxidation with *m*-chloro-perbenzoic acid. In the fourth stage, lactone acid **72** was

Scheme 10. Reagents and condition : (a) NaH , $CH_2(CO_2Me)_2$, $Pd(Ph_3P)_4$, (b) Me_4NOAc , 1,3-dimethylimidazolidin-2-one, 95°, (c) $MeC(OMe)_2NMe_2$, 150°, (d) I_2 , (e) Bu_3SnH , $AIBN$, (f) $DIBAL$, (g) salt-free $Ph_3P=CHEt$, (h) KOH , then CH_2N_2 , (i) $Na_2Cr_2O_7$, H^+ , acetone, (j) $ClCO_2Et$, Py , (k) NaH , $CH_2(CO_2Me)_2$, $Pd(Ph_3P)_4$, (l) K_2CO_3 .

transformed into enol ether **73** (*Z/E* mixture) via the corresponding acid chloride, aldehyde and Wittig olefination of the latter. Acidic hydrolysis of **73** and then Wittig reaction under 'salt-free' condition gave lactone **21** (*Z/E* = 96/4). Purification by MPLC gave pure lactone **21**, which was hydrolyzed in presence of base and then esterified to give ester **22**. Finally, oxidation with pyridinium dichromate in CH_2Cl_2 afforded (+)-**6**. This synthesis provides (+)-**6** in a high state of purity. The overall yield from **68** (18 steps) was 12.5%.

The second enantioselective synthesis of (+)-methyl epijasmonate (**6**) reported by Kitahara *et al.*²⁹ in 1991

Scheme 11. Reagents and condition : (a) cyclo-C₅H₆, (b) LiOH, THF-H₂O, (c) KI₃, (d) KOH, (e) 175°, 9 h, (f) NaOH, (g) RuO₄ (cat.), NaIO₄, (h) HI, (i) Zn, buffer, (j) MCPBA, (k) (COCl)₂, (l) H₂, Pd/BaSO₄, (m) Ph₃PCHOCH₃, (n) THF : H₂O : AcOH (1 : 1 : 3), (o) Ph₃P=CHEt, salt-free condition, (p) NaOH, (q) CH₂N₂/Et₂O, (r) PDC.

(Scheme 12) took advantage of the ready availability of bicyclic lactone **75**, a useful building block for the synthesis of prostaglandins. Incidentally, both the isomers of **75** have become available via optical resolution of the precursor **74**. A sequence of reactions involving DIBAL reduction, treatment with TsOH/MeOH, epoxidation followed by reduction with LAH gave an inseparable mixture of alcohols **76**. Acetal **77** was obtained from **76** by a series of straightfor-

Scheme 12. Reagents and condition : (a) Zn, NH₄Cl, (b) DIBAL, (c) TsOH, MeOH, (d) MCPBA, (e) LiAlH₄, (f) PDC, (g) (MeO)₂P(O)CH₂CO₂Me, NaH/THF : DMF (1 : 1), (h) H₂, PtO₂, EtOAc, (i) 75% AcOH aq., 60°, (j) Ph₃P(Br)CH₂Et, *n*-BuLi, DME, (k) KOH aq., MeOH, (l) CH₂N₂/Et₂O, (m) H₂CrO₄/Et₂O.

ward reactions, namely, oxidation, Horner-Wittig reaction and stereoselective hydrogenation. Hydrolysis of cyclic acetals **77** with warm 75% aqueous AcOH followed by a 'salt-free' Wittig reaction gave a *cis-trans* mixture of bicyclic lactones **21** (*Z/E* = 89/11). Chromatography using silica gel impregnated with AgNO₃ gave pure (*Z*)-lactone **21** which, on mild alkaline hydrolysis followed by esterification, then afforded *cis*-cyclopentanol **22** (~100% *ee* by HPLC analysis of Mosher ester). Finally, two phase oxidation with chromic acid using Brown's procedure gave (+)-**6**, contaminated

Scheme 13. Reagents and condition : (a) Ti(O-*i*Pr)₄, (b) NaH, BnBr, -20° to RT, (c) HI, (d) LiAlH₄, (e) Dess-Martin oxidation, (f) LiO(MeO)C=CH₂, ether, -78°, (g) *N*-methyl-*N,N'*-dicyclohexylcarbodiimidium iodide, THF, (h) Et₂Zn, Ni(acac)₂, THF, 25°, 4 h, then CuCN.2LiCl, then 1-bromobutyne, -55°, 48 h, (i) H₂, Pd/BaSO₄, Py, (j) BCl₃, CH₂Cl₂, -78° to -10°, (k) Dess-Martin oxidation.

with 3% *trans*-isomer **2**. The overall yield from (+)-**74** (13 steps) was 20%.

In 1995, Stadtmüller and Knochel³⁸ published a short enantio- and diastereoselective synthesis of (+)-methyl epijasmonate (**6**) as shown in Scheme 13. Here chiral alcohol **81** was obtained by the asymmetric addition of dialkylzinc **78** to aldehyde **79** in presence of a catalytic amount of **80**. Alcohol **81** was benzylated, desilylated, and removal of the pivalate group with LiAlH₄ followed by oxidation using Dess-Martin periodinane gave aldehyde **82**. The cyclization precursor **83** was obtained as a 1 : 1 diastereoisomeric mixture when **82** was treated with the enolate of methyl acetate followed by *N*-methyl-*N,N'*-dicyclohexylcarbodiimidium iodide. The stereoconvergent radical ring closure of **83** with Et₂Zn, Ni(acac)₂ and 1-bromobutyne gave cyclized product **84** with a 100% *trans*-diastereofacial se-

lectivity and 95% diastereoselectivity. Lindlar reduction of **84** followed by benzyl group deprotection using BCl_3 furnished (–)-**5**. Finally, Dess–Martin oxidation of **5** gave (+)-**6** with 95% *cis*-selectivity (90% *ee*). Overall yield of (+)-**6** was 6.5% in 11 steps.

Borm and Winterfeldt³⁹(1996) reported a formal enantioselective synthesis of (+)-**6** as described in Scheme 14. In this process, chiral cyclopentadiene **87**, prepared from Hajos–Wiechert ketone **86**⁴⁰, was used as a chiral template for a Diels–Alder reaction (involving kinetic resolution) with

Scheme 14. Reagents and condition : (a) Michael addition, (b) L-proline, 1 N HClO_4 , (c) $\text{HS}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{SH}$, H^+ , (d) $\text{Na}/\text{liq. NH}_3$, (e) PCC, (f) PhLi , (g) HBr , (h) 4-acetoxycyclopent-2-ene-1-one, ZnCl_2 , (i) $\text{CH}_2(\text{CO}_2\text{Me})\text{CO}_2$ allyl, K_2CO_3 , 18-C-6, (j) LDA, *cis*- $\text{BrCH}_2\text{CH}=\text{CHCH}_2\text{CH}_3$, (k) HCO_2H , NEt_3 , $\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_2$, (l) NaBH_4 , (m) 405° , (n) H_2 , Pd/CaCO_3 .

4-acetoxycyclopent-2-ene-1-one. Incidentally, Hajos–Wiechert ketone **86** was prepared⁴¹ from 2-methylcyclopentane-1,3-dione (**85**) in two steps involving Michael addition and asymmetric cyclization. The reaction of diene **87** with 4-acetoxycyclopent-2-ene-1-one in a high pressure cycloaddition/elimination sequence, catalyzed with zinc chloride, provided cyclopentenone adduct **88**. Subsequent β -selective Michael addition of allyl methyl malonate followed by diastereoselective alkylation with (*Z*)-1-bromo-2-pentene gave ketone **89**. Palladium catalyzed cleavage of malonate followed by a highly diastereoselective borohydride reduction provided α -alcohol **90**. Heating alcohol **90** at 405° af-

forded the enantiomerically pure allyl alcohol **91** and regenerates the chiral template **87**. Compound **91** on selective hydrogenation gave (–)-**5**. This constitutes a formal synthesis of (+)-methyl epijasmonate (**6**).

Very recently, a truly practical and elegant enantioselective synthesis of (+)-methyl epijasmonate (**6**) from the cyclopentenone derivative **92**, has been accomplished by Fehr and Galindo, from a Swiss perfumery and flavour company (Firmenich, Geneva), as highlighted in Scheme 15⁴².

Scheme 15. Reagents and condition : (a) LiAlH_4 , or (a) PMHS, $\text{Zn}(\text{2-EH})_2$, NaBH_4 then aq. NaOH , (b) $\text{CH}_2(\text{CO}_2\text{Me})_2$, KHCO_3 , novozym 435[®], 40° , 8 torr, (c) NaH/THF , then TMSCl, (d) NMP, H_2O , NaCl , 140° , (e) $(\text{CF}_3\text{CO})_2\text{O}$, H_2O_2 , Na_2CO_3 , (f) $\text{BF}_3\cdot\text{OEt}_2$, CH_2Cl_2 .

The pivotal steps of this synthesis include an enzyme-catalyzed enantioselective mono-esterification with dimethyl malonate, a Claisen rearrangement of the malonate derived allylic silyl ketene acetal and a highly stereoselective epoxidation-rearrangement sequence. Enone **92**, was reduced to alcohol **93** with LiAlH_4 or with polymethylhydrosiloxane (PMHS) and catalytic amounts of zinc 2-ethylhexanoate ($\text{Zn}(\text{2-EH})_2$) and NaBH_4 . The (*R*)-enantiomer of alcohol **93** was transformed to (*R*)-**95** (97% *ee*) in the presence of dimethyl malonate and catalytic amounts of Novozym 435[®]. In this step, enantiomeric alcohol (*S*)-**94** was unaffected (89% *ee*) and could be readily racemized in aq. H_2SO_4 /

THF and recycled. Malonate **95** was converted into the thermally labile silyl ketene acetal **96** which underwent [3,3]-sigmatropic rearrangement leading to **97**. Desilylation and decarboxylation of the rearranged product **97** gave **98**. *syn*-Selective epoxidation of **98** using trifluoroperacetic acid yielded exclusively *syn*-epoxide **99**. It should be noted that the trisubstituted double bond in **98** was epoxidized much faster than the disubstituted one; only 5% of di-epoxidation product was obtained. Finally, Lewis acid catalyzed ($\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{OEt}_2$ or AlCl_3) stereocontrolled suprafacial 1,2-H migration of epoxide **99** afforded *cis*-jasmonate **6** (97% *ee*) contaminated with 6% of its C-2 epimer **2**. It may be noted that these Lewis acids proved to be the most effective ones over other Lewis acids that were tried including LiClO_4 in ether, valuable for acid-sensitive systems, or trimethylsilyl triflates. The overall yield was 37.5% based on recycled **93**. Alternatively, **95** was prepared by enantioselective reduction of **92** using a borane-complexed oxazaborolidine (60%, 92% *ee*), followed by malonate formation (methyl malonyl chloride, triethylamine, 84%).

Enantiospecific (chiral pool) syntheses :

The first chiral pool synthesis of (+)-methyl epijasmonate (**6**) from catalpol **100** (isolated from *Picrorhiza kurroa*⁴³) was reported by Weinges and Lernhardt⁴⁴ in 1990 (Scheme 16). A two-step degradation of catalpol **100**, gave enone **101**, which was converted into cyclopentenone **102** via stereoselective 1,4-thiol addition and 1,2-elimination. So-

Scheme 16. Reagents and condition : (a) $\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, NaH_2PO_4 , $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 10% Pd/C, (b) NaIO_4 , NaHCO_3 , (c) $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{SH}$, Et_3N , (d) MeSO_2Cl , Py, (e) NaBH_4 , (f) NaH, BnBr, (g) $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$, acetone- H_2O , (h) $\text{Ph}_3\text{P}=\text{CHOMe}$, (i) HClO_4 , (j) salt-free $\text{Ph}_3\text{P}=\text{CHEt}$, (k) Na/liq. NH_3 , (l) PDC, (m) CH_2N_2 .

dium borohydride reduction of **102** followed by *O*-benzylation yielded a mixture of **103** (9R : 9S = 12 : 1)^{12,43}. The minor isomer was removed by silica gel chromatography. Treatment of **103** with $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$ in a acetone-water mixture gave lactol **104** which was converted to **105** by a three-step sequence involving Wittig reaction, treatment with perchloric acid and a 'salt-free' Wittig reaction. Removal of the benzyl group of **105** followed by oxidation gave a mixture of epijasmonic acid (**7**) and bridged lactone **21** in the ratio 2 : 1. Lactone **21** can be converted to (+)-**6** according to Helmchen *et al.*³⁷. Finally, esterification of **3** with diazomethane in ether yielded (+)-**6**, which is contaminated with 4.5% of its epimer (-)-**2**.

Another synthesis of (-)-methyl epijasmonate (**6**) was reported in 1997 by Cha *et al.*⁴⁵ and is pictured in Scheme 17. The synthesis starts from commercially available Corey lactone aldehyde **106** which, on Wittig reaction followed by treatment with DBU afforded dienolate **107**. Stereoselective hydrogenation of **107** followed by ester hydrolysis gave 2,3-*cis*-disubstituted-cyclopentane derivative **108**. Oxidative de-

Scheme 17. Reagents and condition : (a) $\text{Ph}_3\text{P}=\text{CHCO}_2\text{Et}$, (b) DBU, CH_2Cl_2 , (c) H_2 , Rh- Al_2O_3 , (d) alc. NaOH then HCl, (e) $\text{PhI}(\text{OAc})_2$, I_2 , (f) RuCl_3 , NaIO_4 , (g) TMSCHN_2 , (h) DIBAL, (i) salt-free $\text{Ph}_3\text{P}=\text{CHEt}$, (j) alc. KOH, (k) TMSCHN_2 , (l) TPAP, NMO.

carboxylation of **108** using $\text{PhI}(\text{OAc})_2\text{-I}_2$ followed by further oxidation with RuO_4 and esterification furnished **63**. Reduction of lactone **63** with DIBAL and the 'salt-free' Wittig reaction of resulting γ -lactol gave lactone **64**. Basic hydrolysis of **64** followed by esterification yielded alcohol **65**. Finally, oxidation of the latter with tetra-*n*-propylammonium perruthenate (TPAP) gave odourless (-)-**6**.

In 1997, Bestmann *et al.*⁴⁶ reported an enantiospecific synthesis of (+)-methyl epijasmonate (**6**) as portrayed in Scheme 18. Construction of the *cis* side-chains was accom-

plished by use of the Diels-Alder reaction between cyclopentenone derivatives **111** and 2-methoxybutadiene with 5 M LiClO₄ in diethyl ether. Cyclopentenone **111** was prepared from (+)-dimethyl-2,3-*O*-isopropylidene-D-tartrate (**109**) in five steps⁴⁷. Diels-Alder adduct **112** was transformed to **113** via a four-step sequence involving reduction of carbonyl group by NaBH₄, protection of the alcohol as TBS-ether, ozonolysis and a 'salt-free' Wittig reaction. It is interesting to note that direct ozonolysis of Diels-Alder adduct **112** followed by a Wittig reaction yielded a *trans*-stereochemistry of the side-chains. This unexpected complete isomerization is probably due to an interaction of the basic phosphorous ylid with the acidic proton in the α -position to the carbonyl function. In addition, ozonolysis also resulted in a mixture of epimeric aldehydes. The removal of the 1,3-

Scheme 18. Reagents and condition : (a) 110 bar N₂, 140°, (b) NaBH₄·CeCl₃·7H₂O, (c) PTSA, acetone-H₂O, (d) 2-methoxybutadiene, 5 M LiClO₄/Et₂O, RT, (e) NaBH₄, EtOH, (f) TBSOTf, 2,6-lutidine, (g) O₃, CH₂Cl₂, then PPh₃, then Ph₃P=CHEt, (h) FeCl₃·6H₂O (cat.), SiO₂, CHCl₃, (i) ClC(S)OC₆F₅, Py, DMAP, (j) 1,3-dimethyl-2-phenyl-1,3-diazaphospholidine, THF, (k) TBAF, (l) Dess-Martin oxidation, (m) [(Ph₃P)CuH]₆, H₂O, bz.

dioxolan moiety of compound **113** was initiated by ketal cleavage with FeCl₃·6H₂O supported on silica gel and deoxygenation using the Corey-Winter reaction to give compound **114**. Removal of the silyl protection from **114** followed by Dess-Martin oxidation yielded enone **115** without

any detectable isomerization. Finally, selective reduction of the conjugated double bond with the Stryker reagent gave **(+)-6** contaminated with 20% of its C-2 epimer.

In 1998, Sarkar *et al.*⁴⁸ reported the enantiospecific synthesis of **(+)-methyl epijasmonate (6)** starting from **(S)-(+)- γ -hydroxymethyl- γ -butyrolactone (116)** as highlighted in Scheme 19. Here the epijasmonoid building block **52** is prepared from chiron **119** using similar ene cyclization methodology as described previously (*cf.* Scheme 8)³⁵. *tert*-Butyldimethylsilyl protection of commercially available **(S)-**

Scheme 19. Reagents and condition : (a) TBDMSCl, Im, (b) DIBAL, THF, -78°, 1 h, Ph₃P=CHCO₂Me, -78° to RT, 5 h, (c) TBDPSCl, Im, (d) PPTS, EtOH, (e) (COCl)₂, DMSO, (f) NaN(TMS)₂, Ph₃P(CH₂CH₂CH₂TMS)Br, THF, (g) 235°, 18 h, (h) 57% HI aq., benzene, (i) O₃, (j) Ph₃P(Pr)Br, NaN(TMS)₂, THF, (k) *n*-Bu₄NE, (l) H₂CrO₄/ether.

(+)- γ -hydroxymethyl- γ -butyrolactone (116) (prepared from L-glutamic acid) followed by reduction with DIBAL and *in situ* Wittig reaction yielded alcohol **117** with 95% *ee*. The enantiomeric excess was determined by conversion to Mosher esters with both *R*-**(+)-MTPA** and *S*-**(-)-MTPA** and ¹⁹F-NMR analysis of the diastereomers. Alcohol **117** was transformed to α -alkoxyaldehyde **118** via a three-step sequence involving protection of the secondary alcohol by TBDPS-Cl, selective deprotection of the TBDMS ether and Swern oxidation. Wittig reaction under 'salt-free' conditions of aldehyde **118** gave chiron **119**. It may be noted that when the phosphonium salt and NaN(TMS)₂ were stirred at room temperature for 1 h, and α -alkoxyaldehyde **118** added to it at -78°, the *E/Z* ratio was about 1 : 1. These experimental conditions usually work very well with ordinary aldehydes for the synthesis of *(Z)*-olefins. When the ylid, Ph₃PCHCH₂CH₂TMS was added within 10 min of its preparation to aldehyde **118** at -78°, the yield as well as

Table 1. Chronological list of the contributions to the synthesis of methyl epijasmonate

Year	Author	Starting material	Sequence length	Products	Scheme no.	Ref.
1975	Torii	2-Cyclopentenone	13	(±)-6	2	23
1987	Kitahara	2-Allylcyclohexane-1,3-dione	10	(±)-6	3	26
1988	Crombie	5-Vinyl-2-norbornene	10	(±)-6	4	27
1989	Monforts	(+)-Monoacetate of cyclopent-2-ene-1,3-diol	9	(-)-6 ^a	10	30
1990	Helmchen	Fumarates of (<i>S</i>)-ethyl lactate	18	(+)-6	11	37
1990	Weinges	Catapol	13	(+)-6	16	44
1990	Seto	Norbornene	10	(±)-6	5	25
1991	Kitahara	3-Oxocyclopentane carboxylic acid	14	(±)-6	6	31
1991	Kitahara	Bicyclic lactone 74 ^b	13	(+)-6	12	29
1992	Stork	2-Cyclopentenone	9	(±)-6	7	33
1994	Sarkar	1,4-Butanediol	14	(±)-6	8	34
1995	Knochel	3-Trimethylsilylacrolein	11	(+)-6	13	38
1996	Winterfeldt	2-Methyl cyclopentane-1,3-dione	15 ^c	(+)-6 ^d	14	39
1997	Cha	Corey lactone aldehyde 106	12	(-)-6	17	45
1997	Bestmann	(+)-Dimethyl-2,3- <i>O</i> -isopropylidene- <i>D</i> -tartrate	15	(+)-6	18	46
1998	Sarkar	(<i>S</i>)-(+)- γ -hydroxymethyl- γ -butyrolactone	12	(+)-6	19	48
1999	Clive	3-Iodo-1,1-dimethoxypropane	21	(±)-6 ^d	9	36
2000	Fehr	Cyclopentenone 92	6	(+)-6	15	42

^aContaminated with 40% of (+)-2. ^bAvailable from Fuji Chemicals Industry Co. Ltd.^c7 steps, on the basis of recyclable chiral template⁸⁷. ^dFormal synthesis.

stereoselectivity (*E/Z* = 16/84) were improved. The remaining steps of the synthesis from **119** are as described before

for the racemic series (*cf.* Scheme 8). The overall yield of (+)-6 from **116** is 4.6% in 12 steps.

Strategy evaluation

All the syntheses discussed in this article are listed in Table 1 in chronological order and include the name of the principal author. The cardinal points to be considered for any rational synthesis of methyl epijasmonate are : (i) *cis* relationship of the two side-chains of the cyclopentane ring, one of which is prone to ready epimerization; (ii) stereochemistry of the pentenyl chain at C-2 should be 'Z'; (iii) absolute configuration of the molecule as a whole and (iv) total number of steps should not exceed 15, if one has to go by the Hudlicky maxim⁴⁹.

Analysis of the syntheses of methyl epijasmonate reveals that, with the exception of Fehr synthesis, all other syntheses either proceed through methyl cucurbate (**5**) or methyl epicucurbate (**22**) in which all substituents on the cyclopentane ring have a *cis*-relationship to each other and require a careful oxidation. Except in few cases^{39,42,46}, in all other syntheses a 'salt-free' Wittig reaction has been used to generate the *cis*-olefin. It transpires that when the C-3 hydroxyl group is *trans* to the C-2 side-chain, either in pro-

tected or unprotected form, the Wittig reaction always gives exclusively the (*Z*)-isomer. However, when C-2 and C-3 substituents are *cis*-disposed, stereoselectivity poses a problem. For example, when the hydroxyl group at C-3 position is protected, stereoselectivity is still high (eq. 3,4). But with an unprotected hydroxyl group (at the C-3 position) up to 15% *trans*-olefin contaminates the desired product (eq. 1,2). This necessitates purification by tedious AgNO₃-SiO₂ chromatography or by MPLC. It may be noted that in contrast to γ -lactols **120**^{29,30} and **121**²⁷, the δ -lactols **123**³¹ and free aldehyde **124**²⁶ give the *cis*-olefins **41** and **5** exclusively. It is tempting to hypothesize that the *cis*- γ -lactols mostly exist in the cyclic form (not aldehyde form) and therefore, the Wittig reaction becomes much slower than those with **123** and **124** in which the aldehyde form is predominant or exclusive, and thereby gives rise to a mixture of olefins²⁹. However, based on the premise that a slow reaction should generally be a more selective reaction, this anomalous behavior is difficult to understand.

In order to discuss the merits and shortcomings of the various syntheses of methyl epijasmonate, we prefer to classify the syntheses into two groups: those using a cyclic starting material and those using an acyclic starting material.

In the racemic series, six syntheses make use of cyclic starting materials of which the earliest synthesis of methyl epijasmonate (**6**) by Torii²³ is essentially a path-breaking one showing methyl epicucurbate (**22**) as an important precursor to (\pm)-**6**. The drawback of this synthesis is that the last oxidative step used to making (\pm)-**6** is likely to have resulted in considerable epimerization at C-2^{24,25}. Kitahara's³¹ second synthesis is an improvement of the first one²⁶ in terms of stereochemical control and overall yield; however, the weak points of the synthetic planning entail reduction of the ketone in the fifth step, subsequent protection of the alcohol, deprotection and eventual regeneration, thus lengthening the synthetic sequence. There is little strategic novelty in Crombie's²⁷ synthesis of (\pm)-**6**; note that this synthesis is based on a previous synthesis of (\pm)-methyl jasmonate (**2**) by Stevens *et al.*²⁸, with the difference that diene **30** is prepared by a [3,3]-sigmatropic rearrangement of commercially available **29**. Seto's²⁵ synthesis stands out with an overall yield of 41%, although the stereohomogeneity of the olefinic side-chain is questionable based on our earlier analysis. In Stork's³³ synthesis, a radical-mediated haloacetal cyclization efficiently generates the *cis*-vicinal stereochemistry of the cyclopentane ring in (\pm)-**6**; however, the poor yield in this step reduces the overall yield of this synthesis. Among the remaining two syntheses of (\pm)-

6, our synthesis³⁴ produces the two side-chains of cyclopentane ring with proper stereochemical control by the use of a conceptually novel intramolecular ene reaction. Clive's³⁶ work suffers in the ring-building step in that the two side-chains are *trans*-generated during radical cyclization and additional steps are needed to correct the relative stereochemistry.

In the non-racemic series, four syntheses make use of acyclic starting materials. Helmchen's³⁷ synthesis is the forerunner of all the chiral syntheses of methyl epijasmonate. The synthesis starts with an asymmetric Diels-Alder reaction and involves several interesting transformations leading to the target. The shortcoming of this synthesis is that it is long. Knochel's³⁸ catalytic enantioselective synthesis is conceptually unique and involves a stereoconvergent radical ring closure of **83**. This synthesis avoids a Wittig reaction which is not appreciated in industry (expensive and polluting). Bestmann's⁴⁶ synthesis makes use of a readily available chiral cyclopentanoid building block and it is radically different from all other syntheses. What might have been a short synthesis of **6**, turned out to be a somewhat longer one, in view of the need to preserve the *cis*-side-chain stereochemistry via reduction of the carbonyl group in the seventh step of the synthetic sequence, protection of the resultant alcohol, deprotection and eventual regeneration. Our own synthesis⁴⁸ is an adaptation of the racemic version. The strategy used in this case yields (–)-methyl cucurbate (**5**) as an added bonus. The starting material, e.g. (*S*)-(+)- γ -hydroxymethyl- γ -butyrolactone (**116**), though somewhat expensive, can be made from L-glutamic acid in gram quantity. The starting materials of the remaining six syntheses of chiral methyl epijasmonate (**6**) are cyclic. While the Weings⁴⁴ synthesis involves a complex starting material, e.g. **100**, Monforts³⁰ synthesis is not altogether novel, since conversion of **62** to methyl epijasmonate (**6**) follows steps already worked out in the racemic series. Cha's⁴⁵ synthesis is interesting but makes use of Corey lactone aldehyde (**106**) as a starting material which is expensive. Kitahara's²⁹ synthesis is more practical than the Helmchen synthesis, entailing fewer steps and higher overall yields. Winterfeldt's³⁹ synthesis represents a powerful solution to the synthetic problem in that only six steps are needed to reach (–)-methyl cucurbate (**5**), a precursor to (+)-**6**, from 2-cyclopentenone and the recyclable chiral template **87**. This also avoids a Wittig reaction. The Fehr⁴² synthesis represents the only industrial synthesis of (+)-**6** with high enantiopurity. In this work, cyclopentenone **92** is an interesting starting material as it has been used in both the industrial syntheses of (\pm)-methyl jasmonate (**2**). This is the

only synthesis which both avoids a Wittig reaction, as well as an oxidative transformation leading to (+)-methyl epijasmionate (6). Incidentally, the two industrial syntheses of methyl jasmonate also avoid a Wittig reaction. In our view, this is a truly innovative, short and cost-effective synthesis.

Outlook

The global interest in methyl epijasmionate research, including its biological activities and total synthesis, which has been sustained over a period of more than 15 years in both academic and industrial laboratories, makes interesting reading in view of its small molecular framework and the functionalities it adorns. Does this molecule still have a future as a target for total synthesis? Perhaps a breakthrough may result if biotechnological options are considered based on the biogenetic path shown is Scheme 1 for the production of this material. Maybe the next millennium will witness many innovations in this direction.

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